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1 **Hydrogen as electron donor for copper removal in**
2 **bioelectrochemical systems**

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11

12Abstract

13Hydrogen gas is an attractive alternative electron donor since it is produced in large quantities as a
14side product in the metallurgical industry. Aim of this study was to demonstrate that microbial anodic
15hydrogen oxidation on a non-catalyzed graphite electrode can be coupled with cathodic copper
16reduction in a BES to simultaneously recover copper and produce power. The strategy was first to
17grow an anodic biofilm on acetate, then replace the acetate with hydrogen as electron donor, and
18finally combine hydrogen oxidation with copper reduction in the cathode. The maximum current density
19was 1.8 A/m^2 at -250 mV anode potential vs Ag/AgCl. When coupled with Cu^{2+} reduction, the maximum
20power density was 0.25 W/m^2 at a current density of 0.48 A/m^2 . Anode overpotentials were higher
21compared to acetate oxidation, probably a result of limited hydrogen solubility and transfer.

23Introduction

24Significant volumes of heavy metal containing wastewaters are produced continuously at metal
25producing or electroplating companies. Heavy metals have been proven highly toxic for human,
26microbial and plant life[1,2]. Because heavy metals, even at low concentrations have negative effects
27on the environment, there is a need to remediate metal containing waste streams. Moreover, metal
28resources are finite, making their recycling crucial, since their production and transportation results in
29high energy consumption and arises unwanted and highly pollutant gas, solid and liquid
30emissions[3,4].

31Conventional heavy metal removal technologies include electrochemical, chemical precipitation and
32ion-exchange. Although these technologies are applied in practice and a large scale their economic
33and environmental impact could still be improved by reduction of the high operational costs due to
34chemicals and energy consumption and the reduction of excessive production of hazardous wastes.
35This improvement could possibly also be achieved by the removal of these heavy metals in
36bioelectrochemical systems (BES).[3,5]. In order to improve economic revenue and environmental
37impact of heavy metal treatment, we propose the removal of metals with BES. In BES the costs for
38chemicals and also for energy are minimized, and even power is produced in some cases; the
39biological oxidation of organic substrates provides part of required energy input. Three basic
40components comprises a BES: an anode, where substrate is oxidized and electrons are entering an
41electrical circuit, a cathode where a reduction reaction takes place and electrons are leaving the
42electrical circuit and, in most of the cases, an ion-exchange membrane that keeps the anolyte and
43catholyte separated and prevents substrate/product crossover[6].

44Several metals have been demonstrated as electron acceptors in BES cathodes such as silver [7,8],
45iron [9–11], Nickel [12], zinc [13] and copper [13–19]. A common feature in all these studies is that the
46electron donor in the anodic compartment is an organic substrate. Electrochemically active bacteria
47are efficient oxidizers of organic substrates such as glucose, ethanol, glycerol, cellulose feedstocks,
48sewage sludge and aromatic compounds, but also inorganic such as hydrogen and sulfur
49compounds[20–22]. The use of organic substrates limits application of BESs to certain locations where
50organic wastewaters are available, but in reality organic waste streams are not ubiquitous. At the same

51time, mining and metal industries, being the ones most interested in metal recovery, produce large
52amounts of hydrogen as a side product of their electroplating activities [23,24]. Hydrogen is also
53produced in reduction furnace operations[25] and as a side product of electro-catalytic treatment for
54acidity in mine waters[26,27].

55Hydrogen can be used as electron donor in chemical fuel cells where it reacts with oxygen to produce
56electric current. The drawbacks of fuel cells is that they utilize noble metal catalysts like platinum,
57which are expensive and rare materials, and often operate at extreme conditions [28,29].
58Microorganisms could serve as an alternative catalyst for the hydrogen oxidation reaction. Production
59of current by hydrogenotrophic anodophilic bacteria in MECs has already been reported by a number
60of researchers [30–32]. Rozendal et al. (2008) [33] used hydrogen as electron donor in order to grow a
61bioanode, which was after start-up changed to a hydrogen producing biocathode by reversing the
62polarity of the electrode. Moreover, Wang et al. (2014) [34], succeeded in perchlorate reduction in a
63bioelectrochemical reactor utilizing autotrophic hydrogen oxidizing bacteria. Both studies did not
64analyze the performance of a hydrogen oxidizing biofilm on the anode.

65The main objective of this study was to explore the feasibility to utilize hydrogen as electron donor in
66combination with electrochemically active microorganisms at the anode for the recovery of copper at
67the cathode of a bioelectrochemical system. The strategy was to first to grow an anodic biofilm on
68acetate, then replace the acetate with hydrogen as electron donor and finally couple the hydrogen
69oxidation to copper reduction in the cathode. The performance of this system was studied by analyzing
70current as a function of anode potential, and, when coupled to copper reduction, power production.

72 **Materials and methods**

73 Experimental set up. Two identical cells (biotic and abiotic control) with a surface area of 22 cm² were
74 constructed, as described by ter Heijne et al (2008) [35]. Each of them comprised of two graphite
75 plates (Müller & Rössner GmbH & Co., Troisdorf, Germany) serving as anode current collector and
76 cathode. The anode material was graphite foil (1.0 g/cm³ density, 99% purity; Coidan Graphite
77 Products Ltd., York, UK), which was pressed on the anode current collector.

78 Two plexiglass plates with a single flow channel as middle compartments contained anolyte and
79 catholyte and were separated by a Ralex anion exchange membrane (MEGA a.s., Stráž pod Ralskem,
80 Czech Republic). Two additional plexiglass plates served as temperature control (30 °C) on the
81 outside of the cell.

82 Temperature and pH were continuously logged (Endress + Hauser, Liquiline data logger) through pH
83 electrodes (Endress + Hauser, CPS41 D) that were placed in the recirculation of anolyte and catholyte.
84 In the headspace of each of the recirculation bottles, a gas sampling point was placed. The outgoing
85 gas flow was measured using a bubble counter (MilliGascounter, Type MGC-1, Ritter, Bochum,
86 Germany).

87 Electron donor and electrolyte composition. The anode of both cells was first fed with an acetate
88 containing solution (20 mM) at a rate of 2 mL/min. This solution furthermore contained the following
89 buffer and nutrients: 0.68 g/L KH₂PO₄, 0.87 g/L K₂HPO₄, 0.74 g/L KCl, 0.58 g/L NaCl, 0.28 g/L NH₄Cl,
90 0.1 g/L MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.1 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O and 0.1 mL/L of a trace element mixture [36].

91 The anolyte chamber was operated in a continuous mode and the catholyte in a batch mode. The
92 anolyte was recirculated at 200 mL/min via two recirculation bottles of 0.5 L each. The catholyte was
93 recirculated with the same rate in a 1 L bottle, which was shared by both the biotic and abiotic cell.

94 During stage 1, the bioanode tests on acetate and hydrogen, the catholyte consisted of 10 mM of
95 phospho During stage 1, the bioanode tests on acetate and hydrogen, the catholyte consisted of 10
96 mM of phosphate buffer solution (pH 7). In stage 2, the bioanode coupled to copper reduction, the
97 catholyte consisted of 1 g/L Cu²⁺ (prepared from CuCl₂ and deionized water; pH = 4).

98 The cathode was kept anaerobic by flushing with nitrogen gas.

99In the second stage both cells were fed with hydrogen gas as electron donor. This hydrogen gas inflow
100was controlled with a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst HICH-TECH BV, Ruurlo, Nederland) at 3, 10
101and 30 mL/min. Hydrogen was sparged in the recirculation bottles and continuously recirculated
102through the headspace of the recirculation bottles with a vacuum pump to achieve saturation of the
103analyte with hydrogen. Buffer and nutrients remained the same when the hydrogen gas served as
104electron donor.

105Experimental strategy: The biotic cell was inoculated with a mixed microbial culture from an active
106MFC utilizing acetate as electron donor. The abiotic cell was not inoculated and served as control. This
107cell was tested under the same hydrogen flows as for the biotic cell and with the anode potential
108ranging from -400 to -200 mV.

109Table 1 gives an overview of the two experimental stages. First, the cell was started with acetate as
110electron donor and during the experiment the acetate was first partly and later fully replaced with
111hydrogen. For both cells the anode potential was controlled with a potentiostat ranging from -400 mV
112to -200 mV (50 mV steps), in order to see the response of current generation as a function of the
113anode potential. When a stable current was reached, the acetate concentration was decreased
114stepwise to 10 and 5 mM acetate. For these last two concentrations of acetate the anolyte was flushed
115with 3 mL/min H₂ at the same time. Next, only hydrogen was provided to the cells as a sole electron
116donor with a flow of 3, 10 and 30 mL/min were tested.

117In the second experimental stage, hydrogen oxidation at the anode was combined with copper
118reduction at the cathode. The potentiostat was replaced by an external resistor and the resistance was
119stepwise reduced when the current reached a stable value; 1000, 500, 250, 100, 75, 50 Ω. The
120hydrogen flow provided during these experiments was 30 mL/min, while the catholyte was a

121Copper solution replaced regularly to keep copper concentration constant during the experiment. The
122copper concentration was checked twice every day to be sure that concentration was close to 1g/L,
123and never lower than 0,7 g/L.

124. Finally, bicarbonate was added as carbon source in addition to hydrogen as electron donor (30
125mL/min H₂). Again, the anode potential was controlled with a potentiostat between -400 and -200 mV
126in 50 mV steps.

127The biotic cell was inoculated again a few times during the experiment when a sharp drop in current
128was observed. At these points the system was also supplied with additional acetate. The experiment
129was only resumed when the supplied acetate was completely depleted, as confirmed by IC
130measurements.

131 Table 1 Overview of the three experimental stages for the biotic cell.

Stage of experiment	Electron donor	Anode potential vs Ag/AgCl or value of resistor	Duration (days)	Cathode reaction
1: bioanode development on acetate and switch to hydrogen	20 mM Acetate	-400 mV to -200 mV	10	Hydrogen production
	10 mM acetate + 3ml/min H ₂	-350 mV to -250 mV	8	
	5 mM acetate + 3ml/min H ₂	- 400 mV to -200 mV	8	
	3 ml/min H ₂	- 400 mV to -200 mV	11	
	10 ml/min H ₂	-350 mV and -200 mV	11	
	30 ml/min H ₂	- 400 mV to -200 mV	7	
2. Bioanode on hydrogen coupled to copper reduction and addition carbon source	30 ml/min H ₂	1000 Ω to 50 Ω	14	Copper reduction
	30 ml/min H ₂ + HCO ₃ ⁻	400 mV to -200 mV	15	

132

133

134 Electrochemical control. The anode potential was controlled with a potentiostat (BANK ELEKTRONIK,
135 WENKING POTENTIOSTAT KP 3A5V). Since the anode potential was controlled and the cathode was
136 anaerobic, the cell voltage was negative, such that hydrogen gas was produced in the cathode. The
137 potentials of the cell compartments were controlled and measured versus Ag/AgCl 3M KCl reference
138 electrodes (Qis, QM711X – Reference electrode, Epoxy, Refillable, 4mm) that were placed in the
139 electrolyte, for both the anodic and the cathodic compartment. All potentials are reported versus the
140 Ag/AgCl reference electrode (+0.201 vs SHE).

141 The cell voltage, anode, cathode and membrane potential (defined as the potential difference between
142 the two reference electrodes), as well as the current produced were recorded every minute on a data
143 logger (Endress + Hauser RSG40). Chronoamperometry tests were conducted in order to check the
144 current production of the abiotic cell with different hydrogen flows and anode potential control, using
145 Autolab equipment (Metrohm Autolab B.V., PGSTAT 302N).

146 Analytical procedures and calculations: The acetate concentration in the cells was measured using ion
147 chromatography (Metrohm 761 Compact IC equipped with a conductivity detector and a Metrosep
148 Organic Acids 6.1005.200 ion exclusion column) and the bicarbonate concentration was determined
149 using a total carbon analyzer (Shimadzu TOC-VCPH). The gas composition in the headspace of the
150 cells was also examined with a gas chromatographer (Varian Inc. (Part A) - CP-4900 Micro-GC).

151 When the catholyte was changed to the copper solution, the current and power production were
152 calculated according to

$$153 I = \frac{V_{cell}}{R_{ext} * A_{an}} \quad (2)$$

$$154 P = \frac{V_{cell}^2}{R_{ext} * A_{an}} \quad (3)$$

155 where V_{cell} is the cell voltage, R_{ext} is the external resistance (Ω), A_{an} is the projected surface area of the
156 anode (0.0022 m²).

158 **Results and discussion**

159 **Hydrogen as electron donor for an electroactive biofilm.** The performance of the anodic biofilm
160 with acetate and hydrogen as electron donors is summarized in Figure 1.

161 Initially an acetate solution (20 mM) was used to achieve fast growth of an electroactive anodic biofilm
162 and a stable current. The performance of this bioanode was analyzed at controlled anode potentials in
163 steps of 50 mV (every 50 hours) ranging from -400 to -200 mV. The bioanode produced a maximum
164 current of 3.98 A/m² at -250 mV. After that, the acetate concentration was stepwise decreased while an
165 inflow of hydrogen was introduced to the system. When the acetate concentration decreased to 10
166 mM and 3 mL/min H₂ was flushed in the anolyte, the maximum current density was 1.80 A/m² at -250
167 mV. When the acetate concentration was decreased further to 5 mM, the maximum current density
168 was 0.92 A/m² at an anode potential of -250 mV.

169 In the next experimental stage, after depletion of acetate, the anolyte was provided only with hydrogen
170 at a flow of 3 mL/min. The maximum current density was 0.67 A/m² at an anode potential of -250 mV.
171 This was the highest current obtained during this experimental cycle. Increase of the anode potential
172 to -200 mV led to a slight decrease in current density (0.62 A/m²). These results show that also in
173 absence of acetate, hydrogen can be used as electron donor for the bioanode.

174 Nevertheless, the produced current with hydrogen as electron donor was a factor 6 lower than with
175 only acetate. A possible limitation of current production from hydrogen is the availability of hydrogen
176 gas for the microorganisms, due to its low solubility. To test if hydrogen was limiting, after 11 days, the
177 hydrogen inflow into the anolyte was increased from 3 mL/min to 10 mL/min H₂ gas. For -200 mV (the
178 only anode potential measured at this H₂ flow), the bioanode now produced 1.84 A/m². A further
179 increase of the H₂ gas flow to 30 mL/min and repeating the experiments at anode potentials in the
180 range of -350 to -200 mV did not lead to a further increase in current density. The maximum current
181 density at this hydrogen flow was 1.57 A/m² at an anode potential of -200 mV.

183 **Figure 1- Performance of biotic cell when shifting from acetate to H₂ as electron donor**

184 **Abiotic control experiments.** Hydrogen can be oxidized in the absence of microorganisms at noble
 185 metal based catalysts like Pt. Possibly, it can also be oxidized on a plain graphite electrode. To verify if
 186 the biological catalysis, and not the graphite electrode, was responsible for hydrogen oxidation, the
 187 current produced in an abiotic cell was compared to the current produced in the biotic cell. In Figure 2
 188 the current density obtained from the biotic cell is compared with the current produced from the abiotic
 189 cell, at an anode potential of -200 mV and at different hydrogen inflows. The current density in the
 190 abiotic cell was much lower than the current produced in the biotic experiment at all flow rates. Some
 191 negative current was measured for the abiotic cell, meaning that a reduction reaction, instead of an
 192 oxidation reaction, occurred at -200 mV electrode potential, due to the potentiostatic control of the cell.

193 According to these results, it can be concluded that the electroactive biofilm oxidized hydrogen at the
 194 graphite electrode.

196 **Figure 2 Abiotic cell vs biotic cell performance at an anode potential of -0.200 V at different hydrogen**
 197 **inflow rates.**

198 **Cathodic copper reduction coupled with anodic hydrogen oxidation.** Finally, experiments were
 199 conducted where the electrons from hydrogen oxidation at the bioanode were used to reduce copper
 200 at the cathode. The anolyte was continuously flushed with 30 mL/min H₂ in order to operate at high
 201 hydrogen concentration, while the catholyte was a copper solution ([Cu²⁺]=1 g/L). Copper
 202 concentration was replenished regularly so that copper concentration was always >0.7 g/L.

203 Figure 3A shows the performance of the system in a polarization and power curve. During the
 204 experiment the external resistor was stepwise reduced: 1000, 500, 250, 100, 75 and 50 Ω. The initial
 205 cell voltage and current density obtained with 1 kΩ were 0.61 V and 0.28 A/m², respectively, giving a
 206 power density of 0.17 W/m². The maximum power density obtained was 0.25 W/m². At that point the
 207 cell voltage was 0.53 V and the current density was 0.48 A/m². The highest current density was 0.66
 208 A/m² in combination with a power density of 0.24 W/m².

209 The following equations show the potentials for acetate and hydrogen oxidation, copper reduction and
 210 the overall cell voltages.

211 Acetate oxidation

213 Hydrogen oxidation

215Copper reduction

217Overall

220Figure 3B shows the anode, cathode and membrane potential and their contribution to the total cell
 221voltage. The maximum cell voltage close to the open circuit voltage was 0.608 V; which is very close
 222to the theoretical open cell voltage of 0.636 V for copper reduction combined with hydrogen oxidation
 223(equation 5). The anode potential close to open circuit was -0.468 V , slightly more positive than the
 224theoretical potential (equation 2). The cathode potential was quite stable throughout the range of
 225measured current densities varying between 0.097-0.141 V, close to the theoretical potential of copper
 226reduction (equation 3). The copper concentration in the catholyte decreased in the course of the
 227experiment, indicating that indeed copper was recovered at the cathode. Copper recovery and its
 228efficiency was not further analyzed in this study, but has been analyzed by others [37].

229As can be seen from this figure, both the membrane and cathode potential are stable over the whole
 230current range. The drop in cell voltage at higher current densities is caused by increase in anode
 231potential. This increase in anode potential is most likely caused by limited transport of hydrogen
 232towards the biofilm. Even though the gas flow was increased hydrogen supply to the biofilm might be
 233limited due to its limited solubility in water at atmospheric pressure.

234

235 **Figure 3 (A) Power and polarization curve for hydrogen oxidation coupled to copper recovery and (B)**
236 **contribution of the anode, cathode and membrane potential to the cell voltage.**

237

238 **Perspectives and long term performance.** The results presented here show the proof of principle for
239 the use of hydrogen as electron donor for the recovery of copper in BESs. The current and power
240 densities obtained in this study (0.48 A/m^2 in combination with 0.25 W/m^2) are in the same order as
241 previous investigations of copper removal in BESs. However, all previous studies used an organic
242 electron donor while here for the first time hydrogen was used. Tao et al. produced 0.26 W/m^2 power
243 density at 0.86 A/m^2 current density [18], using glucose as electron donor. Ter Heijne et al obtained a
244 maximum power density for acetate oxidation coupled to copper reduction of 0.43 W/m^2 at a current
245 density of 1.7 A/m^2 in exactly the same cell configuration as used in this study [16].

246 Second, our analysis of overpotentials shows that the anode overpotential for hydrogen oxidation is
247 higher than for acetate oxidation. A probable reason for this higher overpotential is limited hydrogen
248 availability due to its low solubility, even at higher flow rates. A future configuration should avoid these
249 limitations, for example through more efficient gas transport and elevated gas pressure.

250 Finally, the long term performance of this system should be investigated. Hydrogen acts only as an
251 electron donor, while microorganisms require also a carbon source for growth. In the final stage of our
252 experiment, we observed a slow decrease in current density, with limitations in carbon source as a
253 possible reason. To test the effect of carbon source, we provided the cell with bicarbonate and were
254 able to run it under stable conditions ($\sim 1.2 \text{ A/m}^2$) for over two weeks (data not shown). It should be
255 further investigated what the minimum requirement of carbon source is and if an inorganic source is
256 sufficient for these microorganisms to survive for long periods of time. For example, Jeremiase et al
257 showed that a hydrogen producing biocathode required two times lower startup time with acetate
258 compared to a biocathode starting on bicarbonate [38]. When adding a carbon source, either in the
259 form of acetate or bicarbonate, care should be taken not to produce methane instead of electricity,
260 since both acetate and bicarbonate are suitable substrates for methanogens. In the present research,
261 already small amounts of methane (max 4%) were detected in the headspace.

262

263 **Conclusions**

264 With a BES, biologically catalyzed hydrogen oxidation at the anode can be coupled with copper
265 reduction. Results show a maximum current density of 0.67 A/m^2 combined with a power density of
266 0.25 W/m^2 when hydrogen is used as single electron donor. Further research and optimization of the
267 system could lead to a novel practical application for BESs for metal recovery.

268

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- 366

Highlights:

- Biological hydrogen oxidation was successfully combined with copper reduction.
- Open circuit voltage was close to theoretical voltage of the cell.
- Power density of 0.25 W/m^2 was achieved at 0.48 A/m^2 .
- Hydrogen solubility was limiting the rate of the process.

Reviewer 1:

Overall I think the paper is clearly written. However, the following information should be added:

-Give information about the chemical composition of the catholyte. This info could be provided in the paragraph on lines 92-95.

The composition of the catholyte has been added to lines 92 to 95:

During stage 1, the bioanode tests on acetate and hydrogen, the catholyte consisted of 10 mM of phosphate buffer solution (pH 7). In stage 2, the bioanode coupled to copper reduction, the catholyte consisted of 1 g/L Cu²⁺ (prepared from CuCl₂ and deionized water; pH = 4).

-Show Cu concentration data. On line 223, it is stated the the Cu concentration in the catholyte decreased. Although the focus of the paper is on the H₂-utilizing anode, there is no reason not to show the Cu data as well (for example in a supplementary material). Also, use the Cu concentration measurements to estimate a coulombic efficiency for the cathode.

The copper solution was replaced regularly to keep copper concentration constant during the experiment. The copper concentration was checked twice every day to be sure that concentration was close to 1g/L and never lower than 0,7 g/L.

-Discuss the possible reactions taking place at the anode. On line 256 it is stated that small amounts of CH₄ was produced during H₂-feed. It is also possible that acetate is produced from H₂ and bicarbonate. That acetate could then potentially be used by the bioanode or by methanogens. Was any acetate detected during feed with only H₂?

Indeed, alternative electron donors besides H₂ could play a role. We did analyze the anolyte for Acetate concentration, and it was below detection limit, on the other hand, methane was detected in the headspace of the cell, likely originating from H₂ and CO₂ We have added this to the text.

-I think the sentence on lines 252-253 should have the word acetate in it somewhere. Please check.

The word acetate has been added to line ...:

Jeremiase et al showed that a hydrogen producing biocathode required two times less time for startup with acetate compared to a biocathode starting on bicarbonate

-Clarify what led you to add bicarbonate in the last phase of the study. Was there any evidence that the bioanode was not stable with only H₂ feed? Or was it just to check if the current could be increased with a higher concentration of the carbon source?

When H₂ was used as energy source for a longer period, current density decreased gradually (data not shown in manuscript) as well known that microorganisms need a carbon source, besides an energy source to survive a longer period of time. Therefore, we decided to demonstrate that a combination of bicarbonate as carbon source combined with hydrogen allowed to maintain the cell performance for a longer period of time or even improve it.

Reviewer 2:

- The focus of the article is clear and experiments are well described.

- In the introduction all the treatments look very bad and only BES are the only good. Comments should be soften.

We have changed line to :

Conventional heavy metal removal technologies including electrochemical, chemical precipitation and ion-exchange. Although these technologies are applied in practice and a large scale their economic and environmental impact could still be improved by reduction of the high operational costs due to chemicals and energy consumption and the reduction of excessive production of hazardous wastes. This improvement could possibly also be achieved by the removal of these heavy metals in bioelectrochemical systems (BES).

- It is not clear excess H₂ in the metallurgical industry for use in the anode. In fact it is usual produce H₂ at the cathode in many BES, as evidenced by numerous articles in this journal

We agree with the reviewer that both processes have been studied before. However, they have not been combined in a single study before; and in addition, the performance of a hydrogen oxidizing bioanode (e.g. as function of anode potential) has not been studied before. This study looks for a combined solution of use the hydrogen oxidation process by bacteria and the copper reduction process, as explained in the introduction: There have been a number of reports of heavy metal removal in BESs. These reports all make use of an organic electron donor. These electron donors are generally not available at sites where heavy metals are produced and their transport to these facilities would be expensive. On the other side, an excess of H₂ is produced in smelting companies in the reduction furnace or by electrochemical production as secondary reaction when nickel, cobalt or zinc are plated.

- The main objective of this study is to explore the feasibility to utilize hydrogen as electron donor in combination with electrochemically active microorganisms at the anode for the recovery of copper at the cathode. This approach is not very new.

- Oxidation of H₂ at the anode is known. The reduction of copper is also known.

Oxidation of H₂ at the bioanode is a novel process that has been reported, but its performance has not been studied before. The reduction of copper is not new, but the combination of both processes in a single device is a novel application of this technology, as discussed in the comment above.

- Discussion of results should increase and use less comments in conclusions.

Changes already done in the manuscript.

A

Leeuwarden, July 14th 2015

Editorial Office

International Journal of Hydrogen Energy

Dear editor,

Hereby we would like to submit the enclosed manuscript entitled "Hydrogen as electron donor for copper removal in bioelectrochemical systems" as a research paper for *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*.

The recovery of heavy metals is an important challenge in the hydrometallurgical industry. Recently, the recovery of copper coupled to oxidation of organic matter in a bioelectrochemical system was proposed as a viable option. However, organic electron donors are not always available on-site. Hydrogen gas is an attractive alternative electron donor since it is produced in large quantities as a side product in the metallurgical industry. The aim of this study was to demonstrate that microbial anodic hydrogen oxidation on a non-catalyzed graphite electrode can be coupled with cathodic copper reduction in a BES to simultaneously recover copper and produce power. We show here, for the first time, that it is possible to combine hydrogen oxidation with copper reduction. We believe the results achieved in this study show great promise for the future recovery of heavy metals in bioelectrochemical systems.

We hope you will consider our manuscript for publication in *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*.

Sincerely,

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